

ENDURE

Politics After the Pandemic: Attitudes to Democracy, Authoritarianism, Protest and the “Culture War” Across Six Countries

ENDURE – Cluster 3 Survey Study

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Executive Summary

The COVID-19 pandemic tested democratic societies in ways that extended far beyond public health. Lockdowns, vaccine mandates, and emergency governance measures became flashpoints for deeper conflicts over trust, authority, and national identity. As the immediate crisis receded, questions remained: How do citizens across the Atlantic world now view democracy and its alternatives? What divides have the pandemic years entrenched or revealed?

This report presents findings from a comparative survey conducted in six countries¹ — Brazil, Croatia, Germany, Poland, the United Kingdom, and the United States — at the end of 2024 and beginning of 2025. Drawing on stratified samples in each country, we examine attitudes toward democracy and governance, political interest and mobilization, and positions on contentious “culture war” issues including immigration, ethnic diversity, and sexual harassment. Throughout, we explore how these attitudes vary not only between countries but within them — particularly across those who hold different views about COVID-19 vaccination.

Democratic Attitudes: Widespread Support, Uneven Depth

Across all six countries, large majorities affirm that living in a democracy is important. Yet the depth of this commitment varies. In Germany, Poland, Brazil, and the UK, roughly half or more of respondents describe democracy as “absolutely important.” Croatia is a striking outlier: only about a quarter of Croatians select consider it an imperative, and more than three-quarters view technocratic rule by experts favorably.

Satisfaction with “actually existing” democracy is more equivocal. Germans and Britons express the highest satisfaction, while Brazilians are notably polarized — among the most likely to call democracy “absolutely important” but also the most likely to describe it as a “very bad” system. Brazil also shows the greatest openness to authoritarian alternatives: roughly half of Brazilian respondents view a “strong leader” who ignores congress and elections favorably, compared to a third or fewer elsewhere.

Vaccine Attitudes as a Political Marker

One of the report’s most consistent findings is that attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccination track with a wide range of other political orientations. Respondents who believe the risks of vaccination outweigh the benefits are, across most countries, less satisfied with democracy, more open to authoritarian leadership, more hostile to ethnic diversity, and more likely to feel that attention to sexual harassment has “gone too far.”

This pattern is especially pronounced in the United States, where vaccine skepticism appears tightly bundled with a broader constellation of conservative views. In the UK, by contrast, vaccine skeptics diverge less sharply from the mainstream on other political questions —

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suggesting that the American pattern of pandemic polarization may be distinctive rather than universal.

Mobilization: Interest Without Action

Political interest remains relatively high across the six countries. Germany leads in engagement, with more than 40% of German's describing themselves as "very interested." Yet interest does not straightforwardly translate into mobilization. Nearly half of British and American respondents say they would "never" attend a lawful demonstration — the highest rates of protest aversion in the study — despite robust traditions of political mobilization in both countries.

In Brazil and Croatia, respondents living in neighborhoods marked by visible social disorder (proxied by public alcohol consumption) were more likely to have protested and were more willing to do so again. Elsewhere, the pattern was reversed: neighborhood deprivation was associated with withdrawal from political participation. This suggests that the relationship between local conditions and civic engagement is shaped by national context.

The "Culture Wars"

Attitudes toward ethnic diversity and sexual harassment reveal both cross-national variation and within-country divides. Americans were by far the most favorable toward increasing ethnic diversity, while Croatians and Poles were the most hostile. On sexual harassment, Brazilians, Croatians, Germans, and Poles were more likely to feel that attention to the issue had "not gone far enough," while Americans and British respondents were more divided.

In the United States, Germany, and to a lesser extent the UK and Poland, positions on these issues cluster together: those who view ethnic diversity positively also tend to feel more attention to harassment is needed, and vice versa. This alignment fits the "culture war" framing familiar from Western political discourse. But in Brazil and Croatia, these attitudes operate more independently — suggesting that the bundling of cultural positions observed in North America and Western Europe does not generalize to all national contexts.

Implications

These findings offer a mixed picture of democratic resilience in the post-pandemic moment. On one hand, outright rejection of democracy remains rare, and political interest is broadly sustained. On the other hand, pockets of authoritarian sympathy exist in every country surveyed, and the pandemic appears to have crystallized — or at least made visible — attitudinal divides that extend well beyond public health. Vaccine skepticism, in particular, has become a marker of broader worldview orientations, especially in the United States. Whether these divides will fade as the pandemic recedes, or harden into durable political cleavages, remains an open question.

1. Introduction

Democracy in a Post-Pandemic World

The COVID-19 pandemic exposed fault lines in public trust, amplifying existing inequalities, and entangling public health with deeper conflicts over authority, identity, and the democracy. Across the Atlantic world, governments imposed unprecedented restrictions on movement, assembly, and economic life. Vaccination became a site of political contestation. Movements on both left and right — from Black Lives Matter to anti-lockdown protests — mobilized under conditions that might have seemed to preclude collective action.

Concerns about democratic backsliding predate the pandemic but have intensified in its wake. The election of Donald Trump in 2016, the rise of populist parties across Europe prompted a wave of scholarship on the fragility of established democracies. The pandemic added new dimensions to these debates: emergency powers invoked by executives, the politicization of scientific expertise, and public health as a political battleground. How far the pandemic has deepened democratic disenchantment remains an open empirical question.

This report offers evidence on that question from six countries spanning the Atlantic: Brazil, Croatia, Germany, Poland, the United Kingdom, and the United States. Drawing on original survey data collected at the end of 2024 and beginning of 2025, we examine how citizens in these societies view democracy and its alternatives, how engaged they are in political life, and where they stand on contentious cultural issues — immigration, ethnic diversity, gender-based violence — that have come to define contemporary political divides.

The ENDURE Project

This research was conducted as part of ENDURE (Inequalities, Community Resilience and New Governance Modalities in a Post-Pandemic World), a Trans-Atlantic Platform project examining the short- and long-term consequences of the COVID-19 crisis. ENDURE brings together researchers from eleven countries across the Americas and Europe to study how the pandemic has affected inequality, governance, and social resilience. The project is led by Dr. Mihai Varga at Freie Universität Berlin with Soner Barthoma as project coordinator. ENDURE is funded through the Trans-Atlantic Platform's Recovery, Renewal and Resilience program by national science agencies in participating countries: DFG (Germany), FAPESP (Brazil), NCN (Poland), HRZZ (Croatia), UKRI-ESRC (UK), and NSF (USA).

ENDURE is organized into methodological clusters, each deploying different approaches to the study of pandemic consequences. This report presents findings from Cluster 3, which uses survey methods to examine political attitudes and mobilization in comparative perspective. While the broader ENDURE project spans eleven nations including Canada, Colombia, Finland, Romania, and Turkey, the present analysis is limited to the six countries where national funding supported the survey component.

The survey was designed by Peter Ramand and Kristinn Már Ársælsson and administered by Qualtrics in Croatia, Poland, Germany, the UK and the US, and by Netquest in Brazil.

Scope of This Report

This is a descriptive report which presents cross-national and within-country variation in political attitudes and behaviors. The survey instrument included experimental components, the results of which will be published separately. Here, we focus on the pre-treatment measures—the baseline attitudes respondents reported before exposure to any experiment—which provide a comparative snapshot of political orientations across the six countries.

We organize the findings around three broad themes: attitudes toward democracy and alternative forms of governance; political interest and mobilization; and positions on “culture war” issues including ethnic diversity and sexual harassment. Throughout, we examine how these attitudes vary across demographic groups and, in particular, across respondents holding different views about COVID-19 and vaccination. The pandemic is the backdrop against which this research was conceived and funded, and vaccine attitudes offer a window into how pandemic-era conflicts may have reshaped and revealed deeper political divides.

Why These Indicators?

In this report we report a small selection of indicators from the wider survey which speak to pressing questions about democratic resilience, political engagement, and cultural polarization in the post-pandemic era. Each reflects both theoretical considerations drawn from relevant scholarly literatures and practical constraints of survey design. We briefly introduce each here.

Democratic Attitudes and Openness to Alternatives

At the heart of debates about democratic backsliding is a simple question: do citizens still value democracy? We measure this directly by asking respondents how important it is to them to live in a country governed democratically. Yet stated importance may not capture the full picture. Citizens may value democracy in the abstract while expressing dissatisfaction with its current performance, or they may be open to alternatives under certain conditions. We therefore also ask respondents to evaluate democracy as a system of governance and to rate alternatives including a “strong leader who does not have to bother with parliament and elections” and technocratic rule by experts rather than elected officials.

The “strong leader” item is particularly salient in the current political moment, and is used widely in comparative research (Stenner, 2005; Norris & Inglehart, 2019). The return of Donald Trump to the American presidency, and the continued success of the far-right across Europe and Latin America have generated considerable scholarly and public debate. We examine not only average levels of support but also how such support varies with political interest, neighborhood conditions, and pandemic-related attitudes.

Political Interest and Mobilization

Democracy requires citizens to participate in it. We measure political interest directly and examine several forms of political action: attendance at lawful demonstrations, signing of petitions, participation in boycotts, and involvement in strikes. These tap different modes of engagement, from low-cost digital activism to organized collective action.

Research on political participation has long noted that engagement is socially stratified: the better-off and better-educated participate more. But crises can disrupt these patterns, drawing previously disengaged groups into political action or, conversely, deepening withdrawal among the marginalized. The pandemic saw both dynamics: mass mobilizations around racial justice and public health, alongside evidence of pandemic-induced apathy and social atomization. We examine whether the relationship between neighborhood conditions and mobilization follows expected patterns of deprivation-linked withdrawal or, in some contexts, the opposite.

Neighborhood Conditions

Social context shapes political attitudes and behavior. A substantial literature links neighborhood deprivation to lower political trust, reduced civic engagement, and greater susceptibility to anti-establishment appeals. We proxy neighborhood conditions using a survey item asking respondents how often they witness alcohol consumption in the streets where they live. This item is drawn from a broader battery measuring perceptions of antisocial behavior and neighborhood disorder.

Public drinking is an imperfect measure of deprivation — its meaning varies across cultural contexts, and it captures perceptions rather than objective conditions. But it offers a consistent indicator across our six countries of the political correlates of different kinds of community. As we shall see, in some countries respondents in high-disorder neighborhoods are more withdrawn from politics; in others, they are more mobilized.

Vaccine Attitudes

The COVID-19 pandemic politicized public health in ways that may have lasting consequences. Attitudes toward vaccination became entangled with broader orientations toward science, government, and individual liberty. In the United States especially, vaccine acceptance and refusal mapped onto partisan divides with remarkable consistency. But the extent to which this pattern holds elsewhere — and whether vaccine attitudes predict positions on issues with no obvious connection to public health — is an empirical question.

We measure vaccine attitudes using two items: whether respondents believe COVID-19 vaccination should be required or left to individual choice, and whether they believe the benefits of vaccination outweigh the risks or vice versa. Throughout the report, we use the latter item to compare “vaccine supporters” (those who see the benefits of vaccines outweighing risks) with “vaccine skeptics” (those who see risks outweighing benefits). This allows us to examine how far pandemic-related attitudes overlap with broader political worldviews.

Ethnic Diversity and Immigration

Few issues have been more central to the “populist moment” than immigration and its effects on national identity. From Brexit to the rise of the AfD in Germany to Trumpism in the United States, anxieties about demographic change and cultural displacement have fueled electoral insurgencies across the Western world. We ask respondents whether increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes their country a better or worse place to live, a measure widely used in comparative research.

This item is drawn from a larger battery on immigration and national identity. As we shall see, cross-national variation is substantial, as is within-country variation by vaccine attitudes and other factors.

Sexual Harassment

The #MeToo movement brought unprecedented global attention to sexual harassment and gender-based violence. We ask respondents whether they feel attention to sexual harassment in their country has gone “too far,” is “about right,” or has “not gone far enough.” This item taps into broader debates about gender, power, and social change that have become incorporated into culture war conflicts in many democracies.

Positions on sexual harassment are of interest both in their own right and as markers of broader orientations toward social liberalism and traditionalism. Research on “culture war” politics suggests that attitudes on gender, race, and sexuality increasingly cluster together, forming a single dimension of cultural conflict that cuts across older economic cleavages. We examine whether this clustering holds across our six countries or whether, in some contexts, positions on gender and diversity operate more independently.

Structure of the Report

The remainder of this report is organized thematically. We begin with attitudes toward democracy and openness to alternative forms of governance, including authoritarianism and technocracy. We then turn to political interest and mobilization, examining both stated engagement and actual participation in various forms of political action. Next, we address culture war issues: attitudes toward ethnic diversity and immigration, followed by views on sexual harassment. We conclude with a summary of key findings and their implications.

Throughout, we present cross-national comparisons alongside within-country variation by political interest, vaccine attitudes, neighborhood conditions, and views on related issues. Figures and tables are embedded in the text; additional analyses are available in the appendix. Methodological details, including sample characteristics and survey administration, are provided in the Data and Methods section.

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For further information about the overall research project please visit endure-project.org.

2. Attitudes to Democracy and Openness to Alternative Forms of Government

Importance of Democracy

We begin by exploring how important people think it is to live in a country that is governed democratically. Democratic values were widely endorsed, but to different extents across the surveyed nations. Around half of respondents across all the countries considered democracy to be “absolutely” important, i.e. select the extreme option on a 10-point scale. Thus, there is a strong core who view democracy as fundamental. Furthermore, an overwhelming majority selects an option above the midpoint, with fewer than 10% in total reporting they think democracy is not important. Nevertheless, some argue that a stronger unconditional support is needed when democracy is challenged.

Figure 1. Note: Level of Importance (1 = Lowest, 10 = Highest). N = 11880.

We found some differences between countries. Croatia stands out with weaker unconditional support compared to the other countries. Around 50% of respondents in the other five countries think democracy is “absolutely important” while only around 25% think so in Croatia. The proportion of US respondents who pick the extreme option is just below 50% and significantly lower than in the other four countries.

Figure 2. Note: 'Absolutely important' = respondents who selected 10 on a 1–10 scale. 95% CIs. N = 11479.

On the other end of the spectrum, we found across all the countries that fewer than 5% thought that democracy was “not at all important”. In fact, the average proportion was less than 3% except in the US where it was around 3.5%. Thus, while democracy is not considered universally important, relatively few think it’s not important at all. In Germany, Poland, and the UK, only about 1% select the lower extreme option.

Figure 3. Note: 'Not at all important' = respondents who selected 1 on a 1–10 scale. 95% CIs. N = 11479.

Satisfaction with Democracy

As well as being asked about the importance of democracy, respondents were asked to rate various systems of governance (from bad to good), of which a democratic political system was one. We can thus compare ratings of importance and satisfaction.

Attitudes were more equivocal regarding actually existing democratic systems: respondents were asked to rate various systems of governance, of which democracy was one. Only in Germany, the UK and US did a majority describe democracy as a “very good” system, and nowhere did this reach a threshold of 60% (figure5).

Figure 4. Note: Lower values = more favorable views (1 = Very Good, 4 = Very Bad), 95% CIs. N = 11023.

While the patterns are similar across these two measures, one thing to note is that while Brazilians feel that democracy is important, close to 40% are not satisfied, saying that having a democracy is either fairly or very bad. We also observe that while US respondents felt democracy was somewhat less important compared to e.g., Germany and the UK, we see smaller differences in satisfaction. Nevertheless, the highest overall levels of satisfaction were in Germany and the UK.

Figure 5. Note: Question asks 'Having a democratic political system.' Scale from 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11023.

Satisfaction with democracy varied both between and within countries. Germany and the UK were among the most satisfied with democracy as a system of governance, with between 55 and 60% saying having democracy is “very good” and fewer than 5% thinking it is fairly or very bad. In contrast, about 40% or fewer reported high satisfaction in Brazil, Croatia, and Poland. Interestingly Croatians, who were less likely to think democracy was important, report a more comparable satisfaction rating. These findings suggest that the measures tap into different constructs, arguably importance and satisfaction.

Figure 6. Note: Proportion of respondents who described a democratic political system as "Very good." Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. N = 11023.

Brazilian respondents expressed the most polarized attitudes to democracy and democratic rule. Brazilians were among the most likely to describe democracy as “absolutely important” but were the least likely to describe having a democratic political system as a good thing. When looking at dissatisfaction, i.e., respondents who say that democracy is “very bad” we found a somewhat different pattern. Brazilians were significantly more likely to say that democracy was “very bad”, with about 10%, compared to 5-7% in Croatia, Poland, and the US. We found limited strong dissatisfaction in Germany and the UK.

Figure 7. Note: Proportion of respondents who described a democratic political system as "Very bad." Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. N = 11023.

Next, we explore whether democratic satisfaction varies across levels of political interest, views about COVID, social order, and gender values. First, we observe that those “not at all interested” in politics are less satisfied and more dissatisfied with democracy. For example, more than 50% of Polish respondents who say they are “very interested in politics” think that democracy is “very good” compared to less than 25% among those who are “not interested at all”. The same applies for dissatisfaction. Consider the UK for example. Very few among politically interested respondents are dissatisfied but about 25% among the disinterested say that democracy is either “fairly” or “very” bad.

Figure 8. Note: Lower values reflect more favorable views of democracy (1 = Very Good, 4 = Very Bad). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. Analysis includes only respondents who were ‘Very interested’ or ‘Not at all interested’ in politics; other levels of political interest excluded. N = 11023.

We also observe that those who thought that people should be free to choose whether to accept COVID vaccination and those who thought that the risks of vaccination outweighed the benefits were less satisfied with democracy. The differences are on average smaller for the former item compared to the latter. Additionally, we see limited difference in Croatia and Germany between those who prefer required vs optional vaccinations. However, there is a clear difference in Germany between those who think the benefits outweigh the risks and vice versa, with the latter being less satisfied with democracy.

In Germany, a similar relationship can be observed between attitudes towards vaccines and democracy, with 70% of pro-vaccine respondents describing democracies as “very good,” more than twice the number of Germans concerned with vaccine risks.

The confluence between anti-vaccine sentiment and dissatisfaction with democracy appears to be the strongest in Brazil. More than half of Brazilian vaccine skeptics described democratic political systems as “very” or “fairly” bad, compared to a quarter of vaccine proponents (figure

10). Support for authoritarian leadership was also more pronounced among Brazilian vaccine skeptics than in any other country, with three quarters describing an anti-democratic leader as “very” or “fairly” good. A similar, though less dramatic, pattern held across all the other countries surveyed: in the United States, United Kingdom, Germany, Croatia and Poland, vaccine skeptics were consistently more favorable toward authoritarian leadership than vaccine supporters.

Figure 11. Note: Question asks 'Having a democratic political system.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Analysis limited to respondents with views on alcohol consumption in the streets ('Never' vs. 'Extremely often'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 2900.

Figure 10. Note: Question asks 'Having a democratic political system.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Analysis limited to respondents with views on vaccinations ('Benefits outweigh risks' vs. 'Risks outweigh benefits'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 8448.

We found more muted differences across respondents who report higher levels of alcohol consumption in the streets. In Brazil those who say they see consumption extremely often are **more** satisfied than those who say “never”. In the US, we see the opposite, and perhaps more expected trend, that those who experience more social disorder are somewhat less satisfied. American respondents who reported living in neighborhoods where alcohol is consumed in the streets “extremely often” were twice as likely to have a negative perception of democracy (28%), than individuals who said alcohol is “never” drunk openly where they live (14%). However, across all the countries combined, the differences are relatively muted.

Finally, respondents who thought that social attention to sexual harassment had gone “too far” were on somewhat less satisfied with democracy. However, these differences seem to be a little bit larger in Brazil, Croatia, and Poland compared to Germany, the UK, and US.

Figure 12. Note: Question asks 'Having a democratic political system.' Responses coded from 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Analysis limited to respondents with views on societal attention to sexual harassment ('Too far', 'About right', 'Not far enough'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10466.

Openness to Authoritarianism

As well as asking about attitudes to democracy, respondents were asked whether having a “strong leader who does not have to bother with congress/parliament and elections” would be a good or bad way of governing their country. In five out of the six countries, fewer than 50% agreed that it was either “fairly” or “very” good to have a “strong leader” that doesn’t have to “bother with congress and elections”. The one exception was Brazil, with just over 50% thinking it would be good to have a strong leader. Overall, Polish respondents were the least favorable towards authoritarianism with more comparable trends in Croatia, Germany, the UK, and US.

Figure 13. Note: Question asks 'Strong leader does not have to bother with congress and elections.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10908.

There was comparable variation in whether respondents thought authoritarian leadership was “very good” compared to “very bad”. However, the patterns were somewhat different. Fewer than 5% of Polish respondents thought a strong leader was a “very good” idea compared to 20% in Brazil. The second strongest support of authoritarianism was in Croatia and the US, with about 11-13% selecting the extreme option. Germany and the UK showed relatively limited interest in such leadership, with around 7.5% support. The differences between Brazil, Croatia and the US, Germany and the UK, and Poland respectively, were statistically significant.

Figure 14. Note: Respondents who described 'strong leader without Congress/elections' as 'Very good.' 95% CIs, N = 10908.

At the opposite end of the spectrum, we found that opposition to authoritarianism was strongest in Poland and the UK, with close to 50% saying it was a “very bad” idea. Croatia, Germany, and the US were not far behind with between 40 and 43% strongly opposing a leader who can bypass the legislature and elections. However, Brazil was again the outlier with only about 25% of respondents strongly opposing authoritarianism.

Figure 15. Note: Respondents who described 'strong leader without Congress/elections' as 'Very bad.' 95% CIs, N = 10908.

The Polish result reinforces the anti-authoritarian current noted above: despite widespread dissatisfaction with existing democratic performance, Poles were the most hostile to strong leaders flouting democratic norms.

Next, we explore variation in support and opposition to authoritarianism across levels of several covariates. We found that those less interested in politics were both less likely to strongly favor or oppose a strong leader. They were more likely to have weak opinions about authoritarianism.

Among respondents who were “very interested” in politics, opposition to a strong leader was generally stronger. This was apparent in Germany and the UK, but not in Brazil where even politically engaged respondents showed relatively higher tolerance for authoritarian alternatives.

Figure 16. Note: Question asks 'Strong leader does not have to bother with congress and elections.' Responses coded from 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Displayed by level of political interest ('Very interested' vs. 'Not at all interested'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10908.

A similar trend describes the difference between those who prefer vaccinations be required vs optional. However, those who believe the risk of vaccination outweighs the benefits were more likely to think a strong leader was a good idea, and also less likely to think it was a bad idea. In the United States, when asked for their opinion about a “strong” political leader who would “not have to bother with congress” and elections, nearly half of American vaccine skeptics described this as “very” or “fairly” good, compared to half of vaccine advocates who indicated this was “very” bad and an additional 25% who said authoritarianism was “fairly” bad. In Brazil, less than 50% of vaccine proponents said a strong leader was good, but about 2/3 of skeptics. These are clear lines of tension.

Figure 17. Note: Question asks 'Strong leader does not have to bother with congress and elections.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Analysis limited to respondents with views on COVID vaccination requirements ('Everyone vaccinated' vs. 'Individual decide'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10652.

Figure 18. Note: Question asks 'Strong leader does not have to bother with congress and elections.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Displayed by vaccination views ('Benefits outweigh risks' vs. 'Risks outweigh benefits'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 8349.

US respondents living in neighborhoods reporting excessive antisocial behavior were less concerned by the prospect of an authoritarian takeover. Where alcohol consumption is witnessed regularly, more than 50% of respondents described a regime led by an authoritarian

leader as broadly good, compared to only 25% of people who live where alcohol is never publicly consumed. A similar relationship holds between neighborhood drinking and authoritarian attitudes in Germany, with nearly a fifth of respondents in high alcohol consumption neighborhoods describing an illiberal leader as “very good,” more than double the frequency of individuals living in (presumably) affluent areas. In Brazil, we observed the opposite pattern. Those who observed social disorder more frequently were **less** in favor of authoritarianism. However, the differences were less stark compared to the US.

Figure 19. Note: Question asks 'Strong leader does not have to bother with congress and elections.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Displayed by reported frequency of alcohol consumption in the streets ('Never' vs. 'Extremely often'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 2878.

The average rating in the countries was around “fairly bad” (3 out of 4) except for Brazil with a rating between “fairly good” and “fairly bad” (2.5 out of 4). Overall, there is opposition to authoritarianism, but a deeper look shows pockets of support which might be able to turn neutral and weak supporters.

Figure 20. Note: Lower values = more favorable views of authoritarian leadership (1 = Very good, 4 = Very bad). 95% CIs. N = 10908.

Technocracy - Let the Experts Decide

We also asked whether respondents felt that experts, rather than government, should make decisions. Attitudes toward technocratic governance—having “experts, not government, make decisions”—was the most popular alternative to democracy. Across all six countries, large majorities viewed expert rule favorably, with Croatia the most enthusiastic (more than three quarters rated it as “very” or “fairly” good). Unlike attitudes to authoritarian leadership, views on expert governance showed only modest variation by vaccine attitudes: in most countries, both vaccine supporters and skeptics were broadly favorable toward expert decision-making. This suggests that the appeal of technocratic rule cuts across the attitudinal divides that otherwise structure preferences for democratic versus authoritarian governance.

We found that, on average, that participants were either somewhat positive or split on whether technocrats should play a larger role in public policy. Respondents in Brazil and Croatia were a little bit more positive towards expert rule, with similar average scores across Germany, Poland, the UK, and US. In Brazil and Croatia close to 75% said they thought it was either “fairly” or “very” good to have experts make decisions instead of government. Respondents in the other countries were split down the middle.

Figure 21. Note: Lower values = more favorable views of technocracy (1 = Very good, 4 = Very bad). 95% CIs. N = 10835.

Figure 22. Note: Question asks 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10835.

We did not find much difference in views towards technocracy between the politically interested and disinterested. In Croatia and Poland, political enthusiasts were a little bit more positive, while the disinterested were more favorable in Germany.

Figure 23. Note: Question asks 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Displayed by political interest ('Very interested' vs. 'Not at all interested'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 3872.

Many might expect that views on technocracy would be split across vaccine proponents and skeptics due to the central role experts played during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, we found limited differences between those who favored and opposed mandatory vaccination, or whether risk perception. The US, though, was an exception. There we see that those who thought vaccination should be a choice were less positive towards technocracy compared to those in favor of a mandatory vaccination.

Figure 24. Note: Question asks 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Faceted by views on COVID-19 vaccination requirement ('Everyone vaccinated' vs. 'Individual decide'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10586.

Figure 25. Note: Question asks 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Faceted by views on vaccinations ('Benefits outweigh risks' vs. 'Risks outweigh benefits'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 8288.

In contrast, we found that opinions diverge across those who never experience alcohol consumption in the streets compared to those who are consistently exposed. Perhaps surprisingly, in most countries, the more one experiences social disorder the more likely one is

to support expert rule. For example, the proportion of those saying technocracy is a “very good” idea was two times higher among those with more alcohol in the streets. Croatia is an exception where we found the opposite pattern.

Figure 26. Note: Question asks 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Responses coded 1 (Very bad) to 4 (Very good). Faceted by frequency of alcohol consumption in the streets ('Never' vs. 'Extremely often'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 2851.

Key Findings on Attitudes to Democracy

- Brazilians, Germans, and Poles were the most enthusiastic supporters of democracy, with close to 60% of respondents assigning the highest possible score to the importance of living in a democratically governed society. The UK and the US came next, with just above and below 50% support respectively.
- Croatians were the least ardent democrats, with only a quarter indicating that living in a democracy was “absolutely” important to them and three quarters favorable to a technocratic regime — a significant outlier in our survey.
- We found that fewer than 5% said that democracy was “not at all important.” US respondents were the most negative, with about 3.5% selecting the extreme option, followed by Brazil and Croatia with around 2.5%. Only about 1% of survey participants in Germany, Poland, and the UK dismissed the importance of democracy.
- Satisfaction with democracy was somewhat lower among the politically disinterested, vaccination skeptics, and those who perceived social attention to sexual harassment was excessive.
- On average respondents thought that a “strong leader” who doesn’t bother with congress or elections was a “fairly bad” idea. Brazilians were a little bit more positive compared to the other countries.
- Support for authoritarianism was polarized in many countries, with stronger support among politically disinterested, vaccine skeptics, and those who experience more social disorder in their neighborhoods.
- Views on technocracy – expert rule – were split in Germany, Poland, the UK, and US but more positive in Brazil and Croatia. Support for technocracy was relatively stable across levels of political interest, vaccine opinions, and perception of social disorder.

3. Politics and Mobilization

Political Interest

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, political engagement was influenced by factors such as trust in government, media narratives, personal experiences with the virus, and ideological divisions concerning public health responses. Significant mobilizations, despite lockdown measures, were prevalent on the left and right of the political spectrum in the countries surveyed. In the United States, for example, the slaying of George Floyd ignited a protest movement, which thereafter spread internationally, demanding an end to racial injustices. On the other end of the political spectrum, protesters stormed the US capitol building on January 6, and conspiracy inflected mobilizations against government restrictions and lockdown measures emerged across the globe.

Figure 27. Note: Question asks 'How interested would you say you are in politics?'. Responses range from 'Not at all interested' to 'Very interested.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11661.

Political interest varied notably across the societies we surveyed. Germans reported the highest levels of political engagement: more than 82% said they were interested in politics, of which more than half were “very interested”. Croatians and Brazilians were the least engaged, on average, with majority in both countries describing themselves as “not interested,” and a fifth reporting no interest whatsoever. Further investigation is required to ascertain whether or not this is due to demographic skewing within the Croatian sample.

These findings broadly align with existing research on political engagement during crises, which suggest that societies with higher levels of trust in institutions, such as is the case in Germany,

tend to exhibit greater political engagement in times of crisis (Dalton, 2021). Conversely, in nations where public skepticism toward the state is high, political disengagement is likely to be more prevalent (Mudde, 2020).

Figure 28. Note: Respondents who reported being 'Very interested' in politics. 95% CIs, N = 11661.

Figure 29. Note: Respondents who reported being 'Not at all interested' in politics. 95% CIs, N = 11661.

Within countries, political interest also varied according to attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccination. The gap was widest in Germany, where approximately half of those who believed vaccination benefits outweigh risks described themselves as “very interested” in politics (figure 29). On a four-point scale, average political interest ranged from 1.80 in Germany (closer to “very interested”) to 2.63 in Croatia (closer to “not very interested”), with the UK (2.16) USA (2.14) and Poland (2.24) scoring similarly (figure 32).

Figure 30. Note: 'Interest in politics' crossed with views on COVID vaccination requirements ('Everyone vaccinated' vs. 'Individual decide'). Percentages are calculated within each country and vaccination-attitude group. N = 11324.

Figure 31. Note: 'Interest in politics' crossed with 'Benefits outweigh risks' vs. 'Risks outweigh benefits'. Percentages are calculated within each country and vaccination-attitude group. N = 8756.

Perceptions of neighborhood conditions showed a less consistent relationship with political interest. In most countries, respondents reporting frequent alcohol consumption in the streets were somewhat less likely to describe themselves as “very interested” in politics, although this was not true in Poland and the US (figure 30).

Figure 34. Note: Lower values indicate greater political interest ('Very interested' = 1). 95% CIs, N = 1

Mobilization

Examining actual participation, we find substantial cross-national variation. Brazilians (30%) and Germans (28%) were the most likely to report having attended a lawful demonstration at some point in their lives. Brazil's high rate of mobilization is particularly notable given the relatively low levels of political interest reported in that sample, suggesting that factors beyond conventional political engagement drive protest participation there. Croatia followed with approximately 18% reporting participation, while Poland, the UK, and the United States clustered at lower levels, between 13% and 17%. The US figure is striking given the country's high-profile protest movements in recent years, from the Occupy movement to the Black Lives Matter demonstrations following George Floyd's murder in 2020.

Figure 35. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Figure 36. Note: Respondents who reported they have participated in a protest or demonstration. 95% CIs, N = 11018

Rejection of protest as a political tactic is, in many ways, as revealing as past participation in understanding cross-national patterns of mobilization. Nearly half of respondents in the UK

(48%) and the United States (46%) said they would “never” attend a lawful demonstration. These are the highest rates of protest aversion in the study. This is notable for two countries with strong traditions of political mobilization and relatively high levels of political interest. Croatia showed the lowest protest aversion at approximately one in five. Brazil, Poland and Croatia form a middle tier at around 30%. The Anglo-American pattern of protest aversion deserves further investigation: despite robust democratic institutions and freedoms that protect the right to demonstrate, a sizable minority of citizens in these countries appear particularly reluctant to exercise this form of political voice.

Figure 37. Note: Respondents who reported they would never participate in a protest or demonstration. 95% CIs, N = 11018.

Vaccine attitudes reveal a complex relationship with mobilization. Among those who believe the benefits of vaccination outweigh the risks, previous protest participation and willingness to protest were generally higher across most countries. In Germany, for example, approximately 35% of vaccine supporters reported having attended a demonstration, compared to around 25% of vaccine skeptics.

However, the relationship between vaccine skepticism and protest aversion varies considerably by national context. In the UK, for example, vaccine skeptics showed comparable or slightly higher rates of past protest participation than vaccine supporters, and similar proportions expressed willingness to protest in the future. In the United States, conversely, vaccine skeptics were substantially more likely to say they would “never” attend a demonstration (55%) compared to vaccine supporters (40%). This suggests that American vaccine skepticism may be associated with a broader withdrawal from conventional political participation, consistent with research linking health skepticism to political alienation (Oliver and Wood, 2014). British vaccine skeptics, meanwhile, appear less politically disengaged than their American

counterparts, a finding consistent with patterns observed elsewhere in this report. In Brazil, both groups showed relatively high mobilization, though vaccine supporters maintained a modest edge in past participation.

Figure 38. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Results are shown by opinions on COVID vaccination requirement (law: everyone vaccinated vs. choice: individual decide). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Social scientists have noted that mobilization is strongest when crises intersect with existing political cleavages (Tilly, 2004). The US reports some of the deepest ideological and effective divisions, which subsequently mapped on to how individuals interpreted and responded to the pandemic. In contrast, Poland and Croatia’s lower mobilization rates perhaps reflect broader trends of political apathy in post-communist societies (Howard, 2003).

Prior findings suggest that beliefs concerning health can be a major driver of political mobilization. Studies by Oliver and Wood (2014) have shown that public health skepticism often aligns with distrust in political institutions, which can either fuel protest movements or lead to withdrawal from politics (as seen in Poland and Croatia). Research by Jennings et al. (2022) has found that support for vaccines is often associated with trust in science and governance, both of which correlate with higher political engagement. In contrast, vaccine hesitancy is frequently linked to political alienation and conspiracy belief systems (Hornsey et al., 2021). We find support for this in most cases, but note cross-national variation which should be investigated further.

Figure 39. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Results are shown by respondents' views towards vaccinations (benefits outweigh risks vs. risks outweigh benefits). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Political interest emerged as the strongest and most consistent predictor of protest participation across all six countries. Among respondents who described themselves as “very interested” in politics, rates of past protest participation were dramatically higher than among the disengaged. In Brazil, for example, more than half of highly interested respondents reported having attended a demonstration, compared to fewer than 15% of those “not at all interested” in politics, a threefold difference. Similar patterns held in Croatia (approximately 48% versus 15%), Germany (38% versus 23%), and Poland (30% versus 20%).

The relationship between political interest and willingness to protest in the future follows a similar gradient. Across all countries, those with higher political interest were more likely to say they “would” attend a demonstration and less likely to say they “would never” do so. In Poland, for instance, more than 50% of politically disinterested respondents said they would never protest, compared to approximately 20% among the highly engaged.

Notably, even among the politically disinterested, we observe cross-national variation in protest aversion. Croatians who reported no interest in politics were nevertheless more open to demonstration attendance than their counterparts in the UK, US Germany or Poland, with fewer than 40% ruling out protest entirely compared to nearly three quarters of respondents in the Anglo-American and German cases. This suggests that national political cultures shape baseline willingness to mobilize independent of individual-level political engagement.

Figure 40. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Results are shown by political interest ('Very interested' vs. 'Not at all interested'). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Neighborhood conditions, as proxied by reported street alcohol consumption, showed a complex relationship with mobilization across cases. In general, respondents in high alcohol consumption neighborhoods were somewhat more likely to say they “would never” attend a demonstration, consistent with the link between neighborhood deprivation and alienation from political participation (figure 39). However, this was not uniform: in Brazil and Croatia, the opposite is observed, with respondents in deprived neighborhoods more likely to have protested and more willing, on average, to do so again in the future.

Demonstrations represent only one form of political action surveyed. In the appendix, we present data on signing electronic petitions, joining boycotts, and participating in strikes (figures 86, 88, 90). Petitions were, by far, the most common form of participation across all countries, with more than half of all respondents reporting having signed one, and fewer than 15% saying they “would never” do so. Boycotts occupied a middle position, while strike participation was the least common.

Mobilization: Attend a lawful demonstration
Perceptions of Societal Attention to Sexual Harassment

Figure 42. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Results are shown by respondents' perceptions of societal attention to sexual harassment (Too far, About right, Not far enough). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Mobilization: Attend a lawful demonstration

Opinion that having a democratic political system is a good way to run your country

Figure 43. Note: Question asks 'Now I will list different forms of political action that people can take. For each of these, please tell me whether you have done any of these, might do, or would never do: Attend a lawful demonstration.' Responses are grouped as 'Have done,' 'Would do,' and 'Would never do.' Results are shown by respondents' opinion on whether having a democratic political system is a good way to run their country (Very good, Very bad). Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11018.

Key findings on interest in politics and mobilization

- Germans reported the highest levels of political interest (43% “very interested”) and were among the most likely to have attended a protest (28%), alongside Brazilians (30%). Croatians and Brazilians were the least likely to be politically engaged, on average, with more than a fifth of respondents in each country describing themselves as “not interested in politics”.
- Despite relatively high mean interest in politics, nearly half of British and American respondents said they would “never” attend a lawful demonstration—the highest rates of protest aversion in the study. Germany showed the lowest aversion (25%).
- Vaccine attitudes shaped mobilization in country-specific ways.: in the US, vaccine skeptics were less likely to have protested; in the UK, the pattern was reversed, with skeptics marginally more mobilized than vaccine supporters., with 55% saying they would “never” do so. In the UK, this pattern was reversed, with vaccine skeptics showing comparable rates of mobilization to supporters.
- In Brazil and Croatia, respondents in neighborhoods with visible public drinking were more likely to have protested and more willing to do so again—the opposite of patterns observed elsewhere, where neighborhood deprivation was associated with withdrawal from political participation.
- Petitions were by far the most common form of political action across all countries, with more than half of respondents reporting having signed one and fewer than 15% ruling it out. Boycotts occupied a middle position, while strike participation was least common.
- Political interest was generally the strongest correlate of actual protest participation, with the “very interested” several times more likely to have attended a demonstration than the “not at all interested” across most countries.
- Respondents who felt attention to sexual harassment had “not gone far enough” showed higher rates of past and future mobilization. In the UK and US, more than half of those who felt it had gone “too far” said they would never attend a demonstration.”

4. The Culture War: Immigration, Ethnic Diversity and Sexual Harassment

The “culture wars”—affectively charged ideological and political debates concerning issues connected to gender, sexuality, ethnicity and other identities and practices—have been cited as drivers of social and democratic instability. To explore this question, and its broad relationship with the pandemic, we will first explore attitudes to immigration and ethnic diversity, before subsequently considering the breakdown of sentiments regarding sexual harassment and society.

Attitudes to Ethnic and Racial Diversity

With the exception of the US, all countries surveyed indicated net negative sentiment towards increasing ethnic diversity, with a majority of Croatians indicating it makes their societies worse, and a plurality of Poles, Germans and Brits sharing this sentiment.

Americans were, on average, the biggest supporters of ethnic diversity, with more than a third saying that “increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups in the U.S.” make their country a “better” place to live in, compared to only 14% who thought it made it “worse.” (As we shall see below, this sentiment varies substantially within the US population based on where you live and what you think about the vaccine).

Figure 44. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Response categories are shown as 'Better,' 'Makes no difference,' and 'Worse.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11205.

Figure 45. Note: Respondents who said increasing different races and ethnic groups makes their country 'Better,' 95% CIs, N = 11205.

the opposite end of the spectrum, Croatians and Poles were the most hostile to increasing ethnic diversity through immigration, with approximately half of respondents in both countries arguing that it makes their societies “worse,” compared to around ten percent who said the result was social improvement.

Germany and the UK represent something of a middle tier, relative to the other nations, with a quarter responding positively to the effects of growing ethnic diversity. Most Brazilians say that it makes no difference.

Figure 46. Note: Respondents who said increasing different races and ethnic groups makes their country 'Worse.' 95 CIs, N = 11205.

The relationship between vaccine skepticism and hostility toward ethnic diversity was pronounced across most of the countries surveyed, although its magnitude varied considerably. Except for Brazil, vaccine skeptics were more considerably more hostile to growing ethnic diversity than their co-nationals.

The United States showed the starkest divide. Among vaccine supporters, 48% said increasing racial and ethnic diversity makes the country better compared to only 11% who said it makes things worse. Among vaccine skeptics, these figures are effectively reversed: just 27% viewed diversity positively while 22% saw it as detrimental, representing a swing of more than 30 percentage points in net sentiment.

In Poland and Croatia—countries already characterized by high baseline hostility to diversity—vaccine skepticism amplified these attitudes further. Among Polish and Croatian vaccine skeptics, approximately 70% said diversity makes the country worse, compared to around 45% of vaccine supporters.

In the UK the relationship was more muted: vaccine skeptics were more hostile to diversity than vaccine supporters, but the gap was smaller than in the US or Germany, consistent with the broader finding that British vaccine skepticism does not cluster as tightly with conservative attitudes as it does elsewhere.

In Brazil, the relationship appears to be formally reversed. While majorities among both vaccine supporters and skeptics said changing diversity “makes no difference”, Brazilians worried about the risks of vaccination were more open to ethnic diversity than advocates of the vaccine.

Figure 47. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Response categories are shown as 'Better,' 'Makes no difference,' and 'Worse.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 10966. Results are shown separately for respondents who believe 'Everyone should be vaccinated by law' and those who believe 'Individuals should decide.'

Figure 48. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Response categories are shown as 'Better,' 'Makes no difference,' and 'Worse.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 8536. Results are shown separately for respondents who believe that the 'Benefits of vaccination outweigh the risks' versus those who believe the 'Risks outweigh the benefits.'

Political interest showed a modest but discernible relationship with attitudes toward ethnic diversity, though the patterns varied across countries. In general, engaged respondents were more likely to see the benefit of increasing ethnic diversity. Very interested respondents in

Germany, the UK, and the United States were the most likely to view diversity positively. Among Americans “very interested” in politics, approximately half said diversity makes the country better, compared to approximately a quarter of those not at all interested. While in Germany and Britain more than a quarter of the engaged approved of growing diversity, they were nevertheless outnumbered by those who thought it made the country worse.

In Croatia and Poland—the two countries most hostile to ethnic plurality—political interest showed little consistent relationship with diversity attitudes. Highly engaged Poles were as likely to view diversity negatively as their disengaged counterparts. In Central European contexts, skepticism toward immigration and ethnic diversity appears to cut across levels of political engagement, rather than being concentrated among the most alienated as tends to be the case in Western Europe.

In Brazil the relationship is reversed: engaged citizens were far more likely to have a negative view of diversity than the disengaged. Politically disengaged respondents were considerably more likely to say that changing diversity “makes no difference” than the engaged.

Figure 49. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Response categories are shown as 'Better,' 'Makes no difference,' and 'Worse.' Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 4017. Results are shown separately for respondents who report being 'Very interested in politics' versus those who are 'Not at all interested in politics.'

Perceptions of alcohol consumption in the streets seemingly did not correlate with negative impressions of diversity and immigration. In the US and Croatia, we observe the opposite: neighborhood residents who witnessed regular alcohol consumption were more likely to see immigration as beneficial (in Croatia this was by a factor of three). Notably, while neighborhood deprivation may correlate with illiberal attitudes in the form of authoritarian leadership, our findings suggest it does not correlate with hostility to ethnic diversity.

Figure 50. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Responses shown: Better / Makes no difference / Worse. Percentages are calculated within each country. Facets compare respondents who report seeing alcohol consumption in the streets 'Never' versus 'Extremely often'; other levels excluded. N = 2964.

Views on ethnic diversity and sexual harassment were also broadly correlated in Germany, Poland, the UK and the US. Respondents who felt that attention to sexual harassment had “not gone far enough” were considerably more likely to view increasing diversity as making their country “better,” while those who felt it had gone “too far” were more likely to view diversity as making things “worse”. This is consistent with “culture war” frames that see positions on race and gender aligned along a single dimension of social liberalism versus traditionalism.

In the United States, the alignment is particularly striking. Among respondents who felt attention to sexual harassment had “not gone far enough,” around half said increasing diversity makes the country better, while fewer than 10% said it makes things worse.

Germany and the UK displayed similar patterns. Respondents concerned about harassment in both countries were around twice as likely to view diversity positively compared to those who felt it had attracted too much attention. In Poland the same pattern held although it was less dramatic.

Brazil and Croatia diverged from this pattern. In these countries, views on sexual harassment showed little consistent relationship with diversity attitudes. Brazilians across all three harassment perception groups were similarly likely to say diversity “makes no difference,” while Croatians were similarly hostile regardless of their views on harassment. This suggests that the tight clustering of “culture war” attitudes observed in Western Europe and North America may not travel to all national contexts. In Brazil and Croatia, positions on gender and immigration appear to operate more independently.

Figure 51. Note: Question asks 'Would you say that increasing the number of people of different races and ethnic groups makes [COUNTRY] a better or worse place to live, or does it not make much difference?' Responses shown: Better / Makes no difference / Worse. Percentages are calculated within each country. Facets compare respondents' perceptions of whether societal attention to sexual harassment has gone 'Too far', is 'About right', or is 'Not far enough'. N = 10652.

Figure 52. Note: Lower values indicate more positive evaluations of ethnic diversity (1 = 'Better', 3 = 'Worse'). 95%

Attitudes to Sexual Harassment

The “MeToo” movement brought unprecedented attention to sexual harassment across the globe. We asked respondents in each country whether they felt attention to sexual harassment had “gone too far,” was “about right,” or has “not gone far enough.” In Croatia, Germany and Poland, attitudes were broadly similar at the national level: around half indicating that it had “not gone far enough,” compared to between 10-15% who felt it had gone “too far.”

Responses varied substantially across countries, revealing distinct national conversations about gender and power. In Brazil, concern about insufficient attention was highest: around two thirds of respondents said society had “not gone far enough” in addressing harassment, compared to only around 15% feeling it had gone “too far” and one in five saying it was “about right”. Croatia, Germany, and Poland showed similar patterns, with roughly half of respondents in each country saying more attention was needed and 10-15% saying it had been excessive.

Figure 53. Note: Question asks 'In your opinion, when it comes to sexual harassment in [COUNTRY], has society gone too far, not far enough, or is it about right?' Responses shown: Too far / About right / Not far enough. Percentages are calculated within each country. N = 11007.

In the US and UK, fewer respondents—around 36%— felt attention to sexual harassment had been insufficient, while nearly a quarter felt it had gone “too far”. The proportion saying the social response was “about right” was also higher in these two countries, at roughly 40%.

This Anglo-American divergence is noteworthy. Despite the MeToo movement’s origins in the United States and its significant impact in the UK, publics in these countries appear more divided about whether the resulting attention has been appropriate. This may reflect the

intensity of backlash discourse in Anglophone media, or it may indicate that the movement's high visibility in these countries prompted more critical reflection on its scope and methods.

Figure 54. Note: Respondents who said society has 'Not gone far enough' in addressing sexual harassment. 95% CIs 11007.

Figure 55. Note: Respondents who said society has gone 'About right' in addressing sexual harassment. 95% CIs, N 11007.

Figure 56. Note: 1 = 'Too far', 2 = 'About right', 3 = 'Not far enough.' Lower = concern about overreaction.

The relationship between political interest and views on harassment was inconsistent across cases.

In the US, the politically engaged were somewhat more likely to feel that attention to harassment had “not gone far enough” compared to those disinterested in politics, while in Poland and the UK the disengaged were more likely to say that it had gone “too far.”

In Brazil, Croatia and Germany conversely, politically disinterested respondents showed comparable or slightly higher concern about harassment than the engaged. Overall, political interest appears to be a weaker predictor of harassment attitudes than it is for democratic satisfaction or mobilization. Views on gender-based harassment cut across levels of political engagement more than other “culture war” issues.

Figure 57. Note: Question asks 'In your opinion, when it comes to sexual harassment in [COUNTRY], has society gone too far, not far enough, or is it about right?' Responses shown: Too far / About right / Not far enough. Percentages are calculated within each country, separated by levels of political interest. N = 3960.

Vaccine attitudes showed a stronger and more consistent relationship with views on sexual harassment than political interest, reinforcing the picture of COVID-related beliefs as markers of broader worldview orientations.

In Brazil, both groups showed high concern, but skeptics were notably more likely to say attention had gone “too far” (approximately 25%) compared to vaccine supporters (approximately 10%). Among respondents who believed vaccine benefits outweigh risks, more than two thirds said attention to sexual harassment had “not gone far enough.”

This relationship held in Poland, the UK and the US, although the baseline differences between these countries meant the patterns manifested differently. In Poland, where overall concern about harassment was relatively high, vaccine skeptics were less concerned than vaccine supporters but were still more concerned than skeptics in the US or UK.

Croatia emerged as partially exceptional, where attitude to the vaccine made little difference in determining average concern about harassment. These findings suggest that attitudes crystallized during the pandemic—particularly around vaccines and public health authority—have become integrated into broader attitudinal packages. In the United States especially, where pandemic response became intensely politicized, vaccine skepticism now appears to predict positions on issues with no obvious connection to public health, including gender-based violence.

Figure 58. Note: Question asks 'In your opinion, when it comes to sexual harassment in [COUNTRY], has society gone too far, not far enough, or is it about right?' Responses shown: Too far / About right / Not far enough. Percentages are calculated within each country, separated by opinion on COVID vaccination requirement (everyone vaccinated vs. individual decide). N = 10782.

Figure 59. Note: Question asks 'In your opinion, when it comes to sexual harassment in [COUNTRY], has society gone too far, not far enough, or is it about right?' Responses shown: Too far / About right / Not far enough. Percentages are calculated within each country, separated by respondents' view towards vaccinations (benefits outweigh risks vs. risks outweigh benefits). N = 8451.

Perceptions of neighborhood conditions showed a counterintuitive relationship with harassment attitudes in several countries. In Brazil, Croatia, Germany, and Poland, respondents who witnessed alcohol consumption in the streets “extremely often” were more likely to feel attention

to harassment had “not gone far enough” compared to those who never witnessed such disorder. In Poland, for instance, fewer than half of those in non-drinking neighborhoods felt more attention was needed, compared to more than 60% of those in areas with higher anti-social behavior.

This relationship did not hold in the US and UK, however, where the observed pattern is closer to the expectations predicted by theories of neighborhood deprivation.

Figure 60. Note: Question asks 'In your opinion, when it comes to sexual harassment in [COUNTRY], has society gone too far, not far enough, or is it about right?' Responses shown: Too far / About right / Not far enough. Percentages are calculated within each country, separated by reported frequency of alcohol consumption in the streets (Never vs. Extremely often). N = 2917.

Key Findings about “Culture Wars”

- Americans were the most favorable toward increasing ethnic diversity, with more than a third saying it makes the country “better” and only 14% saying “worse”. Croatians and Poles were the most hostile, with roughly half viewing diversity negatively.
- Vaccine skepticism was associated with more negative views of ethnic diversity in all six countries, though the gap was smaller in the UK.
- Perceptions of neighborhood deprivation (proxied by street alcohol consumption) did not correlate with anti-diversity sentiment; in the US and Croatia, the relationship was reversed, with residents of high-alcohol neighborhoods more favorable toward diversity.
- Brazilians, Croatians, Germans, and Poles were more likely to feel that attention to sexual harassment has “not gone far enough” (~50–60%), while Americans and Britons were more divided (~36% “not far enough”, 22–24% “too far”).
- In the United States, vaccine attitudes are associated with views on sexual harassment: skeptics were far more likely to say attention had gone “too far”. This pattern was largely absent elsewhere, highlighting the distinctive bundling of political attitudes in the American context.
- In Croatia, Germany, and Poland, respondents in neighborhoods with visible public drinking were more concerned about sexual harassment, the opposite of what neighborhood deprivation theories might predict.
- In the US, Germany, and to a lesser extent the UK and Poland, attitudes toward ethnic diversity, sexual harassment, and vaccine risk cluster together along a single liberal–traditionalist dimension. In Brazil and Croatia, these attitudes appear to operate more independently, suggesting the ‘culture war’ alignment observed in Western democracies does not generalize across all national contexts.

5. Conclusion

Our evidence raises concerns about democratic support. About 50-60% of respondents in Germany, Poland, UK, and US think democracy is absolutely necessary. Croatia is an outlier, with less than 30%. Across all the countries, those who think the risks of vaccination outweigh the benefits are more likely to think that democratic political systems are bad. In the US, the differences between those who see more benefits or risks is particularly stark. Only 8% of those who think the benefits outweigh the risks think democracy is bad but 34% among those skeptical of vaccinations. We see the same trends in support for a strong leader who disregards principles of liberal democracy.

However, political interest remains relatively high, with more than 85% saying they are “not very” to “very” interested in politics. In Germany, only 5% of respondents say they are “not interested at all”. Croatia is, again, an outlier, with over 50% saying they are “not at all” or “not very” interested in politics. While we see some differences in interest across views towards vaccines, they vary between countries and are sometimes small. Arguably the biggest difference was in Germany, with almost 50% of those who see more benefits saying they are “very interested” but only 32% of those perceiving significant risks.

Direct participation in civic mobilization varies between countries. Despite Croatians being the least interested in politics, they were the most likely to either have or be willing to participate in lawful demonstrations (over 75%). In contrast, almost half of respondents in the UK and USA said they would never turn out for such an effort. We noted a consistent trend across all countries, where those who perceive more problems in their neighborhood (drinking in public) were more likely to mobilize. Thus, while many are concerned about apathy among those “left behind”, we argue democratic disenchantment might spur civic action.

Respondents in the US were by far the most open to increasing racial and ethnic diversity, with 85% saying it would make their country better or make no difference. In the other four countries, about 45% thought increasing diversity would make their respective countries worse. Again, we see stark contrast between views about vaccines. For example, in the US, 48% of those who think vaccines are beneficial think diversity makes their country better and 11% worse. In contrast, among those who are concerned about vaccines only 27% were positive towards increasing diversity and 22% thought it would have a negative impact.

We found meaningful differences across countries about attitudes about sexual harassment. In Croatia, Germany, and Poland about half of respondents thought there was too little attention and 15% or less it was too much. In the UK and USA, on the other hand, only about 35% thought there was too little attention and 22% and 24% respectively felt the issue had gone “too far”. Interestingly, we found in most countries (except the US), that those from neighborhoods with visible drinking habits were more likely to think not enough attention was given to sexual harassment. Less than half of respondents who “never” see drinking in the streets of their neighborhood felt more attention was needed but more than 60% where public drinking could be witnessed “extremely often”.

6. Data and Methods

Survey respondents were recruited by Qualtrics in six countries: Brazil, Croatia, Germany, Poland, the United Kingdom, and the United States of America. Data was collected in Brazil in October and November 2024 and from December 2024 to February 2025 in the other countries. Respondents were stratified according to questions about age, gender, and education presented at the beginning of the survey protocol. The survey included two attention checks and only those who passed at least one of those are included in the data presented here.

Table D1 below provides descriptive data about the stratified samples in each country.

Table D1: Stratified Sample

Country	N	Age		Gender		Education				Response Time	
		Median	SD	Female	Male	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Brazil	2049	55	15.7	51.1	48.7	7.7	2.2	1	12	41.4	110.1
Croatia	1381	40	13.8	49.8	49.8	2.9	1.2	1	6	27.4	29.5
Germany	2094	48	15.8	50.2	49.5	4.4	3.5	1	11	24.6	22.8
Poland	2086	43	15.2	52.2	47.4	6.6	1.7	1	10	28.6	32.8
UK	2109	52	16.0	50.2	49.5	4.1	1.6	1	7	27.0	42.3
USA	2161	46	18.1	52.4	47.2	3.9	1.5	1	7	27.8	32.9

Note: Gender shows percent of total respondents (less than 1% of the full sample identified as “non-binary” or “other”). About 5% flexibility in education stratification. Response time in minutes.

Table D2 shows info about the full non-stratified dataset, including those who failed both attention checks.

Table D2: Non-stratified Sample

Country	N	Age		Gender		Education				Response Time	
		Median	SD	Female	Male	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Croatia	4274	34	13.8	40.2	58.5	3.0	1.3	1	6	16.6	99.9
Germany	6929	40	17.3	49.0	50.1	4.0	3.4	1	11	13.2	47.4
Poland	11492	35	14.4	53.9	45.5	6.4	2.0	1	10	13.6	78.3
UK	6911	47	18.3	42.2	57.4	4.1	1.6	1	7	18.6	92.2
USA	5747	34	17.3	49.6	49.2	3.5	1.6	1	7	12.3	37.9

Note: Gender shows percent of total respondents (less than 1% of the full sample identified as “non-binary” or “other”). About 5% flexibility in education stratification. Response time in minutes.

The national samples were stratified to improve representativeness. As seen in table D2, the non-stratified sample skews younger and somewhat less education, with gender bias in Croatia, Poland, and the UK. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that while stratification provides a less biased sample, it does not achieve the standards of probability sampling (random sample). The difference in response time between the stratified and non-stratified samples comes from the fact that only respondents who passed one of two attention checks moved to the second (experimental) part of the survey. The latter attention check was placed close to the end of the survey sections used in this descriptive study.

Further details about the data, including the survey instrument and access to the data used to generate this report are available on the [Endure Project website](#).

Appendix

Types of governance

Figure 61.

Figure 62.

Interest in Politics

Figure 63. Note: Share within country by interest in politics (excl. 'No difference'). N = 10948.

Figure 64. Note: 'Having a democratic political system.' Coded 1(Very bad)-4(Very good). N = 10933.

Figure 67. Note: Share within country by education level. N = 11502.

Figure 68. Note: Strong-leader item by life satisfaction. N = 10820.

Figure 69. Note: Share within country by views on tougher sentencing. N = 11496.

Mobilization: Attend a lawful demonstration
Opinion that having a democratic political system is a good way to run your country

Figure 70. Note: Mobilization by evaluations of democracy (1-4). N = 10467.

Figure 71. Note: 'Having experts, not government, make decisions.' Coded 1-4. N = 10750.

Figure 72. Note: Perceptions of ethnic diversity by interest in politics. N = 11126.

Attention to Sexual Harassment
Government officials use their power to try to improve people's lives.

Figure 73. Note: Harassment attention by views on whether officials improve lives. N = 10898.

Attention to Sexual Harassment

Interest in Politics

Figure 74. Note: Harassment attention by interest in politics. N = 10935.

Nationalism

Figure 75.

Figure 76.

Figure 77.

Figure 78.

Norm Compliance

Figure 79.

Figure 81.

COVID-19

Figure 82.

Figure 83.

Figure 84.

Figure 85.

Figure 86.

Figure 87.

Mobilization

Figure 88.

Figure 89.

Figure 90.

Figure 91.

Figure 92.

Figure 93.

Mobilization: Attend a lawful demonstration
 Young people today don't have enough respect for traditional values

Figure 94.

Mobilization: Attend a lawful demonstration
 Importance of living in a country governed democratically

Figure 95.

Neighborhood Perception

Figure 96.

Figure 98.

Neighborhood perception: Alcohol consumption in the streets

Figure 97.

Sexual Harrassment

Figure 99.